

FROM TRADITIONAL MEDICINE TO MODERN THERAPEUTICS: A
REVIEW OF *MORINGA OLEIFERA*Eman Fatima^{*1}, Minahil Akhtar², Adan Fatima³, Misha Irshad⁴^{*1,2,3}Department of Pharmacy, The University of Chenab, Gujrat, Pakistan⁴Department of Pharmacy, Rashid Latif Khan University, Lahore, PakistanDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21159249>**Keywords***Moringa oleifera*, Phytochemicals, medicine, hypoglycemia, nutritional plant**Article History**

Received: 30 January 2026

Accepted: 14 March 2026

Published: 30 March 2026

Copyright @Author**Corresponding Author: *****Eman Fatima:**emfatima966@gmail.com**Abstract**

Moringa oleifera is a highly valued medicinal and nutritional plant belonging to the family Moringaceae and is widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Different parts of the plant, including leaves, seeds, pods, flowers, bark, and roots, possess significant nutritional, therapeutic, and industrial importance. *Moringa* is rich in essential nutrients such as proteins, vitamins, minerals, amino acids, fatty acids, and dietary fiber, making it an important natural source for combating malnutrition and improving public health. In addition, the plant contains diverse phytochemical constituents including flavonoids, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, tannins, sterols, and glycosides, which contribute to its wide range of pharmacological activities. Experimental and clinical studies have demonstrated that *Moringa oleifera* exhibits potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial anticancer, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, nephroprotective, and neuroprotective properties. These biological effects are mainly attributed to bioactive secondary metabolites such as quercetin, kaempferol, niazimicin, and glucomoringin. Owing to its remarkable therapeutic potential and nutritional richness, *Moringa oleifera* has gained increasing attention in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and biomedical research. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the botanical characteristics, geographical distribution, nutrient composition, phytochemical constituents, and pharmacological activities of *Moringa oleifera*, while also highlighting its traditional medicinal uses and emerging applications in modern healthcare and pharmaceutical industries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been used for healthcare since ancient times and remain important in traditional medicine systems worldwide. Among these plants, *Moringa oleifera* is widely recognized for its nutritional, medicinal, and economic value. Different parts of the plant are used for various purposes, including nutrition, water purification, biofuel production, honey production, and therapeutic applications. Due to its diverse benefits, *Moringa oleifera* has gained significant importance in pharmaceutical and medicinal research (Singh et al., 2020). *Moringa oleifera* is well known for its impressive nutritional and medicinal

benefits. Different parts of the plant, such as the leaves, roots, bark, flowers, seeds, and pods, provide important health advantages. The leaves, flowers, and fruits are very nutritious and can be eaten fresh, cooked, or in powdered form without losing many nutrients. *Moringa* leaves are rich in protein, vitamins, minerals, and natural antioxidants, making them especially useful for combating malnutrition in developing countries. Research shows that *Moringa* has more vitamin A than carrots, more vitamin C than oranges, more iron than spinach, more potassium than bananas, and calcium levels like milk. Additionally, the leaves are a great source of antioxidant compounds

like flavonoids, phenolics, carotenoids, quercetin, and ascorbic acid, which add to their significant health benefits (Singh et al., 2020). *Moringa oleifera* has been traditionally used across cultures to manage various health conditions, including diabetes mellitus, liver disorders, rheumatism, venomous bites, and cardiovascular complications. Owing to its wide range of therapeutic applications, *Moringa* has gained considerable attention as a valuable medicinal plant in modern pharmaceutical and biomedical research (Ashraf et al., 2024). Therefore, this review article aims to provide a comprehensive and updated overview of *Moringa oleifera*, focusing on its phytochemical composition, nutritional and therapeutic properties, physiological mechanisms, and pharmacological safety. In addition, the review highlights both the traditional medicinal uses of *Moringa* and its growing significance in modern pharmaceutical and healthcare industries (Camilleri and Blundell, 2024).

2. Taxonomic Classification

Moringa oleifera belongs to the family *Moringaceae* and is one of the most widely cultivated species of the genus *Moringa*. Taxonomically, it is classified under Kingdom: Plantae, Subkingdom: Tracheobionta, Superdivision: Spermatophyta, Division: Magnoliophyta, Class: Magnoliopsida, Subclass: Dilleniidae, Order: Capparales, Family: *Moringaceae*, Genus: *Moringa*, and Species: *oleifera* [3,13,14]. The plant is commonly known as the drumstick tree, horseradish tree, or miracle tree due to its extensive nutritional and medicinal importance (Pareek et al., 2023).

3. Geographical distribution

Moringa oleifera is widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of the world. The plant is considered native to parts of India, Arabia, and the East Indies, and is now commonly cultivated across Asia, Africa, Latin America, the Caribbean, the Pacific Islands, and several regions of Central and South America. It is also extensively grown in countries such as Ethiopia, Nigeria, the Philippines, Madagascar, Mexico, and Hawaii. Historical records suggest that the species

spread from India to Africa and Southeast Asia during ancient times through trade and human migration. *M. oleifera* thrives well in warm tropical climates with an optimal temperature range of approximately 25–35 °C. It is a deciduous tree that prefers well-drained soils, moderate sunlight, and slightly acidic to alkaline soil conditions, while excessive waterlogging negatively affects its growth. The plant generally starts producing fruits within 6–8 months after cultivation. Due to its adaptability and economic importance, *M. oleifera* is commercially cultivated in many regions worldwide; however, variations in soil type, climate, and environmental conditions may influence its nutritional composition and phytochemical content (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2016).

4. Botanical description

Moringa oleifera Lam., belonging to the family *Moringaceae*, is a fast-growing, drought-resistant deciduous tree widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions. The plant generally attains a height of 5–10 meters, although under favorable environmental conditions it may grow even taller. The tree possesses an open and umbrella-shaped crown with a softwood stem, fragile branches, and a low branching habit. The bark is greyish to brown in color with a corky texture and becomes rough with age, while young shoots and twigs are greenish-white to purplish and covered with fine hairs. The leaves of *Moringa* are tripinnate and arranged alternately along the stem. The leaflets are small, oval-shaped, smooth, and dark green in color, contributing to the plant's high photosynthetic and nutritional capacity. The flowers are creamy white to yellowish-white, fragrant, and borne in loose axillary panicles. These flowers are rich in nectar and play an important role in honey production. The fruit of *Moringa* is a long, slender, pendulous pod commonly referred to as a "drumstick." Each pod contains numerous dark brown seeds with characteristic wing-like structures that aid in seed dispersal. The seeds are rich in oil and possess significant medicinal and industrial importance, particularly in water purification (A.Hamid et al., 2025).

Pods

Leaves

Trees

Flowers

Figure 1. Pods, Leaves, Trees and Flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

5. Nutrient composition

Nutrient Composition of *Moringa oleifera*. *Moringa oleifera* is considered one of the most nutrient-rich plants due to its exceptional content of proteins, vitamins, min leaves, pods, flowers, and seeds contribute significant nutritional value and have been utilized in human nutrition and traditional medicine (Sultana, 2020).

5.1. Mineral Composition

The leaves of *M. oleifera* are particularly rich in essential minerals such as calcium, with more than 4000 mg of calcium. Potassium, magnesium, zinc, iron, and copper. Calcium plays a vital role in bone formation and growth. Studies have shown that moringa leaves contain significantly higher amounts of calcium compared to milk. Approximately 8 ounces of milk provide 300–400 mg of calcium, whereas moringa leaves can supply nearly 1000 mg, and moringa leaf powder may contain Iron is another major mineral present in moringa (Islam et al., 2021). Moringa leaf powder contains approximately 28 mg of iron, which is considerably higher than beef and even spinach. Due to this high iron content, moringa powder has been suggested as a natural alternative to iron supplements and may help in the management of anemia. Zinc is

also abundantly present in moringa leaves, with reported concentrations ranging from 25.5–31.03 mg/kg. Adequate zinc intake is essential for proper growth, reproductive health, and the synthesis of DNA and RNA (Sultana, 2020).

5.2. Vitamin Content

M. oleifera is an excellent source of several vitamins. The leaves contain high levels of beta-carotene, a precursor of vitamin A, which is important for vision, immunity, and skin health. In addition, moringa contains various B vitamins including folic acid, pyridoxine, and nicotinic acid. Vitamins C, D, and E are also present in appreciable amounts. The vitamin composition of moringa may vary depending on environmental conditions and seasonal changes. Research has shown that vitamin A levels are generally higher during the hot-wet season, while vitamin C and iron concentrations tend to increase during the cool-dry season (Islam et al., 2021).

5.3. Protein and Amino Acid Composition

Moringa is recognized as a valuable plant-based protein source. Different parts of the plant contain considerable amounts of protein and amino acids. Research indicates that immature pods contain approximately 20.66% protein and around 46.78% fiber. Amino acid content

has been reported as nearly 30% in pods, 44% in leaves, and 31% in flowers. These proteins include essential amino acids necessary for tissue growth, repair, and metabolic functions, making moringa beneficial in combating malnutrition and protein deficiency (Islam et al., 2021).

5.4. Fatty Acid Composition

Moringa seeds are rich in beneficial fatty acids, particularly polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) such as linoleic acid, linolenic acid, and oleic acid. These fatty acids are known for their cholesterol-lowering and cardioprotective effects. Studies have reported that moringa seed oil contains approximately 76% PUFAs, which makes it a suitable substitute for olive oil in nutritional applications. Immature pods and flowers also contain important fatty acids, including palmitic, linolenic, linoleic, and oleic acids (Islam et al., 2021).

5.5. Fiber Content

The pods of *M. oleifera* are an excellent source of dietary fiber. High fiber content supports digestive health, improves bowel movement, and may help reduce the risk of colon-related disorders, including colon cancer. Due to its low calorific value and high fiber content, moringa is also considered beneficial for weight management and obesity-related conditions (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2016).

5.6. Factors Affecting Nutrient Composition

The nutritional composition of *M. oleifera* varies significantly depending on geographical location, climate, soil conditions, environmental factors, and seasonal variations. Studies have demonstrated that nutrient concentrations differ according to growing conditions, indicating that environmental factors strongly influence the nutritional quality of the plant (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2016).

Table 1. The nutrient compositions of leaves, leaf powder, seeds, and pods (Sultana, 2020)

Nutrients	Fresh leaves	Dry leaves	Leaf powder	Seed	Pods
Calories (cal)	92	329	205	-	26
Protein (g)	6.7	29.4	27.1	35.97 ± 0.19	2.5
Fat (g)	1.7	5.2	2.3	38.67 ± 0.03	0.1
Carbohydrate (g)	12.5	41.2	38.2	8.67 ± 0.12	3.7
Fibre (g)	0.9	12.5	19.2	2.87 ± 0.03	4.8
Vitamin B1 (mg)	0.06	2.02	2.64	0.05	0.05
Vitamin B2 (mg)	0.05	21.3	20.5	0.06	0.07
Vitamin B3 (mg)	0.8	7.6	8.2	0.2	0.2
Vitamin C (mg)	220	15.8	17.3	4.5 ± 0.17	120
Vitamin E (mg)	448	10.8	113	751.67 ± 4.41	-
Calcium (mg)	440	2185	2003	45	30
Magnesium (mg)	42	448	368	635 ± 8.66	24
Phosphorus (mg)	70	252	204	75	110
Potassium (mg)	259	1236	1324	-	259
Copper (mg)	0.07	0.49	0.57	5.20 ± 0.15	3.1
Iron (mg)	0.85	25.6	28.2	-	5.3
Sulphur (mg)	-	-	870	0.05	137

6. Phytochemical Constituent

Extensive phytochemical investigations on *Moringa oleifera* have revealed a highly diverse profile of secondary metabolites responsible for its wide range of biological activities. The plant contains several classes of bioactive compounds including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates,

sterols, terpenoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, and various organic acid derivatives (Sultana, 2020).

Among alkaloids, compounds such as moringine, moringinine, and moringyne have been identified. Flavonoid constituents include quercetin, kaempferol, kaempferitrin, isoquercitrin, and rhamnetin, which are widely

associated with antioxidant potential. Phenolic constituents such as chlorogenic acid, vanillin, phenolic acids, polyphenols, and 4-hydroxymellein contribute significantly to the plant's redox-modulating properties (Khalid et al., 2023).

A notable feature of *M. oleifera* is the presence of glucosinolates and their bioactive derivatives, including glucomoringin, benzyl glucosinolate, isothiocyanates, niazimicin, and related rhamnosyloxy benzyl compounds. These molecules are known for their chemopreventive and anti-inflammatory actions. Sterol components such as β -sitosterol, β -sitostenone, and sterol glycosides have also been reported, along with terpenoid compounds including carotenoids and tocopherols. In addition, glycosidic structures, including cardiac glycosides and other complex glycosylated

molecules, further expand its pharmacological profile (Lopez-Rodriguez et al., 2020).

Other important secondary metabolites include saponins, tannins, lignans, and iridoids. Organic acid derivatives such as citramalic acid, octacosanoic acid, and various esterified compounds, along with fatty acid-related molecules like 9,12,15-octadecatrienoic acid, have also been identified. Overall, the phytochemical diversity of *Moringa oleifera* highlights its strong pharmacological potential, which is largely attributed to the synergistic activity of these secondary metabolite (Srivastava and Ganjewala, 2024).

Some phytochemical constituents of *Moringa oleifera* plant are found in various parts of the plant. According to the literature; these constituents are listed in tabular form in Table 2 (Paikra et al., 2017) and their chemical structures are shown in fig 2 .

Table 2. Phytoconstituents of plant *Moringa oleifera* Lam (Lopez-Rodriguez et al., 2020, Maldini et al., 2014)

Sr. No	Plant part	Extract	Phytoconstituents
1.	Leaves	Aqueous and alcoholic	Niazirin and Niazirinin - nitrile glycosides, 4-[(4'-O-acetyl-alpha-L-rhamnosyloxy) benzyl isothiocyanate, Niaziminin A, and Niaziminin B, three mustard oil glycosides, niaziminin, a thiocarbamate, 4-(alpha-L-rhamnopyranosyloxy)-benzylglucosinolate, quercetin-3-O-glucoside and quercetin-3-O-(6"-Malonyl- glucoside), Niazimicin. Pyrrole alkaloid (pyrrolemarumine 400-O-a-L-rhamnopyranoside) and 4-hydroxyphenylethanamide (marumoside A and B) 4.alpha and gamma-tocopherol.2
2.	Seeds	Aqueous and Hydro-alcoholic	Methionine, cysteine, 4-(alpha-L- rhamnopyranosyloxy) benzylglucosinolate, Moringine, benzylglucosinolate, niazimicin niazirin.
3.	Pods	Hydro-alcoholic	Isothiocyanate, nitrites, thiocarbamates, O-(1heptenyloxy) propyl undecanoate, O-ethyl-4-(alpha-L-rhamnosyloxy) benzyl carbamate, methyl-p-hydroxybenzoate, beta- sitosterol.
4.	Bark	Alcoholic	4-(alpha-L- rhamnopyranosyloxy) benzylglucosinolate.
5.	Flowers	Hydro-alcoholic	D-glucose, quercetin, isoquercetin, kaempferol, kaempferitin and ascorbic acid, protein, D-mannose.
6.	Root	Alcoholic	Moringine, moringinine, spirachin, 1,3-dibenzyl urea, alpha- phellandrene, p-cymene, Deoxy-niazimicine, 4-(alpha-L- rhamnopyranosyloxy)benzylglucosinolate.
7.	Stem	Aqueous and Hydro-alcoholic	4-hydroxyl mellein, vanillin, octacosonoic acid, beta- sitosterone and beta-sitosterol

Figure 2. Chemical structures of phytochemical constituents

7. Pharmacological Activitiy

Moringa oleifera possesses a wide range of pharmacological properties that support its extensive use in traditional and modern medicine. Various experimental studies have demonstrated its antioxidant, antimicrobial, anticancer, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and anti-obesity activities. Different parts of the plant, including leaves,

seeds, bark, roots, and flowers, contain bioactive compounds responsible for these therapeutic effects (Singh et al., 2020).

7.1. Antioxidant Properties

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) can damage cellular components by overwhelming the body's antioxidant defense system, leading to oxidation of lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, and DNA. This oxidative stress is associated

with several pathological conditions, including hypertension, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, and heart failure. Natural antioxidants are generally preferred over synthetic antioxidants because of their safety and therapeutic potential (Gönenç et al., 2013). *Moringa oleifera* leaves are rich in antioxidant phytochemicals such as quercetin, kaempferol, ascorbic acid, β -carotene, rutin, polyphenols, and isothiocyanates, which contribute significantly to their free radical scavenging activity (Cao et al., 1997). A study reported that myricetin isolated from *Moringa oleifera* seeds exhibited greater antioxidant activity compared with α -tocopherol and BHT (Lalas and Tsaknis, 2002). In addition, leaf extracts of *M. oleifera* were found to contain isoquercetin, astragaloside, and cryptochlorogenic acid. These extracts, along with their bioactive compounds, significantly reduced hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2)-induced reactive oxygen species in HEK-293 cells (Vongsak et al., 2015). *Moringa oleifera* seed and leaf extracts were investigated by Maiyo et al., who isolated two bioactive compounds with antioxidant potential. Among them, quercetin-3-O-glucoside (18) exhibited strong antioxidant activity, whereas 4-(β -D-glucopyranosyl-1 \rightarrow 4- α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy)benzylisothiocyanate (43) demonstrated moderate antioxidant effect (Abd Rani et al., 2018). *Moringa oleifera* seed powder demonstrated significant protective effects against arsenic-induced oxidative stress and reduced arsenic accumulation in blood and soft tissues (Gupta et al., 2012). In another clinical study, supplementation with *Moringa oleifera* leaf powder for three months in 60 postmenopausal women significantly lowered serum malondialdehyde levels, indicating reduced lipid peroxidation. The treatment also increased the activities of antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase, along with ascorbic acid levels, thereby confirming the strong antioxidant potential of the plant (Kushwaha et al., 2012) (Singh et al., 2020). In a study conducted on normal and diabetic rats, aqueous leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* demonstrated significant antioxidant activity. Administration of the extract increased the activities of antioxidant enzymes including

superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione S-transferase, while markedly reducing lipid peroxidation levels. These findings indicate the protective role of *M. oleifera* against oxidative stress. The antioxidant effects were mainly attributed to the rich presence of phenolic compounds and flavonoids in the plant extract, which may help protect tissues from oxidative damage in both normal and diabetic conditions (Jaiswal et al., 2013).

7.2. Anticancer Properties

Cancer remains one of the major global health challenges and is considered the second leading cause of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately 9.6 million deaths annually (Singh et al., 2018a; WHO, 2018d). Among the most frequently diagnosed cancers are lung, breast, stomach, prostate, colorectal, and skin cancers. Although significant progress has been achieved in cancer therapy in recent years, the currently available treatment approaches are still associated with several limitations, including toxicity, adverse side effects, and the development of drug resistance. Therefore, the search for safer and more effective anticancer therapies continues to be an important area of research (Kou et al., 2018). *Moringa oleifera* has demonstrated promising chemopreventive and anticancer potential in several experimental studies. A study by Budda et al. (2011) reported that boiled pods of *M. oleifera* reduced both the incidence and multiplicity of tumors in azoxymethane- and dextran sodium sulfate-induced colon carcinogenesis in mice. The observed inhibitory effect on tumor cell proliferation was attributed to bioactive constituents such as niazimicin and glucomoringin. However, subsequent findings by Jung (2014) indicated that cold-water extracts of *M. oleifera* exhibited greater anticancer activity than hot-water extracts, possibly due to thermal degradation of heat-sensitive phytochemicals during extraction. Moreover, cold-water leaf extracts were found to exert cytotoxic effects against lung and liver cancer cells in murine models (Jung et al., 2015). Similarly, Gismondi et al. (2013) demonstrated that *M. oleifera* leaf extract induced approximately 22% cell death and significantly inhibited proliferation of B16F10

murine melanoma cells. The treatment also promoted apoptosis, evidenced by increased apoptotic nuclei in the sub-G1 phase and arrest of the cell cycle at the G2/M phase, alongside elevated expression of the tumor suppressor protein p53. *Moringa oleifera*, like several members of the Brassicaceae family including Broccoli, Cabbage, and Cauliflower, contains distinctive sulfur-containing secondary metabolites known as glucosinolates (Bennett et al., 2003; Fahey et al., 2001). Glucosinolates are nitrogen- and sulfur-rich glycosidic compounds that contribute significantly to the plant's biological activities (Mithen, 2001). Important glucosinolate-derived compounds identified in *M. oleifera* include niazimicin, pterygosperrin, benzyl isothiocyanate, 4-(α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy) benzyl isothiocyanate, and related glucosinolate derivatives (Leone et al., 2015a). These phytochemicals are distributed throughout different tissues of the plant, although their concentration varies depending on tissue type, cultivar, growth stage, and cultivation practices (Amaglo et al., 2010; Holst and Fenwick, 2003). Glucosinolates and their metabolites have been associated with multiple pharmacological effects, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, stress-modulating, and anticancer activities (Bischoff, 2016; Fahey, 2005). Upon tissue disruption, glucosinolates are hydrolyzed by the enzyme myrosinase to produce biologically active isothiocyanates (Fahey et al., 2001). Among these, allyl isothiocyanate has been reported to suppress the growth of both androgen-dependent LNCaP and androgen-independent PC-3 human prostate cancer cell (Bhadresha et al., 2022).

7.3. Anti-inflammatory Properties

Studies on different *Moringa* species have demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory activity. Ethanolic extracts of *M. concanensis* flowers and fruits showed inflammation inhibition of 78.4% and 44.08%, respectively (Rao et al., 2008; Jayabharathi and Chitra, 2011). Similarly, extracts from the aerial parts of *M. peregrina* reduced peritoneal inflammation and decreased vascular permeability (Elbatran et al., 2005). In another study, ethanolic and aqueous seed extracts of

M. peregrina effectively inhibited fresh egg albumin-induced acute inflammation in rats at oral doses of 100–300 mg/kg (Koheil et al., 2011). The anti-inflammatory potential of *M. oleifera* has been mainly associated with suppression of the NF- κ B signaling pathway. Different leaf fractions, including hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and butanol, significantly reduced the production of inflammatory mediators such as IL-1 β , IL-6, PGE2, TNF- α , nitric oxide, and other cytokines in LPS-stimulated macrophages (Arulsevan et al., 2016). Among these, the ethyl acetate fraction exhibited the strongest activity by inhibiting NF- κ B nuclear translocation and enhancing I κ B expression. Similar effects were also observed with fruit extracts of *M. oleifera*. However, higher concentrations, particularly of the chloroform fraction (500–1,000 μ g/mL), showed cytotoxic effects. Furthermore, Kooltheat et al. (2014) reported that ethyl acetate leaf extracts suppressed RelA expression, while hydroethanolic flower extracts reduced inflammatory mediators and pro-inflammatory cytokines including PGE2, IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α , NF- κ B, iNOS, NO, and COX-2 in LPS-induced RAW264.7 macrophages (Tan et al., 2015). The same extract also enhanced anti-inflammatory mediators such as IL-10 and I κ B- α . Among various plant parts, the fruit extract demonstrated the highest inhibitory effect on nitric oxide release in LPS-induced RAW264.7 cells (Lee et al., 2013). Additionally, Sashidara et al. (2009) isolated aurantiamide acetate from *Moringa* species, which was identified as one of the bioactive compounds contributing to the plant's anti-inflammatory activity (Guevara et al., 1999). A study reported that a methanol extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaves significantly reduced the edema-forming effects in both carrageenan-induced and histamine-induced paw edema models (Adedapo et al., 2015). In addition, the extract markedly decreased the number of acetic acid-induced writhes in mice, indicating a strong peripheral analgesic effect. Notably, its analgesic activity at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg was found to be greater than that of the standard drug indomethacin. Further evidence of its anti-inflammatory potential was demonstrated in a study involving atopic

dermatitis in mice and human keratinocytes (Choi et al., 2016). The ethanolic leaf extract significantly downregulated the expression of mannose receptor mRNA, retinoic acid-related orphan receptor γ T (ROR γ T), and thymic stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) in ear tissue. In vitro findings further showed suppression of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) and reduced expression of pro-inflammatory mediators including CCL17, IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-1 β . Similarly, *M. oleifera* pod extract was found to inhibit the expression of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), TNF- α , IL-6, and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) at both protein and mRNA levels. This effect was associated with inhibition of MAPK phosphorylation and suppression of NF- κ B signaling pathways (Sashidhara et al., 2009).

7.4. Antimicrobial Properties

Various studies have reported significant antimicrobial potential in different species of *Moringa*, highlighting their broad-spectrum activity against bacterial, fungal, and waterborne pathogens. *Moringa* species are widely recognized for their traditional use in water purification and antiseptic applications due to their strong antimicrobial properties. In particular, hexane and methanol seed extracts of both *Moringa oleifera* and *Moringa stenopetala* have demonstrated notable inhibitory effects against important waterborne pathogens, including *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae*, and *Escherichia coli* (Walter et al., 2011). Interestingly, many of these extracts showed higher antimicrobial activity at lower concentrations, indicating their potency even in small doses. Further studies have evaluated different solvent extracts of *M. oleifera* for dental-related antimicrobial applications. Ethyl acetate, acetone, and ethanol extracts obtained from seeds, roots, leaves, and their combinations were tested against oral pathogens. All extracts exhibited inhibitory activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*, with ethanol and leaf extracts showing the strongest effects. However, none of the tested extracts showed significant inhibition against *Candida albicans* (Elgamily et al., 2016). In contrast, another study reported that higher concentrations of *M. oleifera* seed

extracts were required to inhibit the growth of *C. albicans*, suggesting concentration-dependent antifungal activity (Saadabi and Abu Zaid, 2011). In addition, ethanolic leaf extracts of *M. oleifera* have been successfully formulated into oral care products such as toothpaste and mouthwash. The formulated toothpaste demonstrated antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. mutans*, and *Candida albicans*, whereas the mouthwash showed general antimicrobial effects (Elgamily et al., 2016). Moreover, ethanol extracts from seeds and leaves have also shown antifungal activity against dermatophytes including *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, and *Epidermophyton floccosum* (Chuang et al., 2007). Overall, these findings strongly support the potential of *Moringa* species as natural antimicrobial agents for applications in water purification, oral hygiene, and treatment of infectious diseases (Das et al., 1957). *Moringa* species (*M. oleifera*, *M. stenopetala*, *M. peregrina*, and *M. concanensis*) show strong antimicrobial activity in different studies using various solvent extracts (aqueous, methanol, ethanol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and hexane). These extracts are effective against many bacterial pathogens, especially diarrhea-causing organisms such as *E. coli*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella*, *Klebsiella*, and *Enterobacter*, with generally stronger activity against Gram-positive bacteria than Gram-negative ones. The activity is mainly due to bioactive compounds like sterols (β -sitosterol, cholest-5-en-3-ol), fatty acids, triterpenes (lupeol, amyrins), and isothiocyanates, which show strong antibacterial effects even in purified form. Some compounds are more potent than crude extracts and can act against both bacteria and certain fungi. Synergistic plant combinations further enhance antibacterial effects, and different plant parts (leaves, seeds, bark, roots) also show varying levels of activity depending on extraction method. In practical use, *M. oleifera* leaf powder has also demonstrated antimicrobial action in handwashing studies, likely due to saponins acting as natural surfactants. Overall, *Moringa* plants are rich in antimicrobial phytochemicals and show broad-spectrum activity, supporting their medicinal

and pharmaceutical importance (Eilert et al., 1981).

7.5. Anti-diabetic Properties

Diabetes mellitus, particularly Type II diabetes, is primarily characterized by insulin resistance, where body cells fail to respond effectively to insulin, leading to impaired glucose uptake and elevated blood glucose levels. In contrast, Type I diabetes is less common and results from insufficient insulin production due to pancreatic β -cell dysfunction. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 422 million people were affected by diabetes in 2014, with the disease causing around 1.6 million deaths globally in 2016. Diabetes is associated with serious complications, including retinopathy leading to vision loss, nephropathy, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, and lower limb amputations. The WHO emphasizes lifestyle modification, including weight management and a balanced diet, as key preventive strategies. At the molecular level, diabetes progression has been linked to oxidative stress and apoptosis of pancreatic β -cells induced by reactive oxygen species (ROS). These highly reactive molecules, due to unpaired electrons, can damage cellular components and impair insulin secretion. Persistent hyperglycaemia further exacerbates oxidative stress, creating a vicious cycle of cellular damage. *Moringa oleifera* has gained significant attention for its potential antidiabetic properties, largely attributed to its rich content of bioactive phytochemicals, including phenolic compounds. These antioxidants are capable of scavenging ROS, thereby protecting pancreatic β -cells from oxidative damage and reducing apoptosis. Key antioxidant constituents such as flavonoids, tannins, carotenoids, tocopherols, and ascorbic acid have been identified in different parts of the plant and are believed to contribute to its

therapeutic effects. Experimental studies have provided substantial evidence supporting the antidiabetic activity of *M. oleifera*. In streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic models, aqueous leaf extracts have been shown to protect pancreatic β -cells by enhancing endogenous antioxidant defense mechanisms and reducing hyperglycaemia. Similarly, α -glucosidase inhibition assays have demonstrated that *M. oleifera* leaves exhibit strong inhibitory activity, with significantly lower EC50 values compared to root extracts, indicating higher efficacy in leaves. Comparable activity to ascorbic acid further supports its potent antioxidant and antidiabetic potential. In addition, phenolic-rich extracts of *M. oleifera* have been reported to inhibit key carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase, thereby delaying carbohydrate digestion and reducing postprandial blood glucose levels. In vivo studies in diabetic animal models have also confirmed a significant reduction in blood glucose following administration of aqueous extracts. The antidiabetic effects of *M. oleifera* are further associated with secondary metabolites such as quercetin-3-glycoside, rutin, kaempferol, various glycosides, and terpenoids. More recently, the presence of insulin-like proteins in seed extracts has been suggested as an additional mechanism contributing to glucose regulation. These proteins have demonstrated the ability to improve glucose tolerance and reduce hyperglycaemia in experimental diabetic models. Overall, the cumulative evidence indicates that *Moringa oleifera* exerts antidiabetic effects through multiple mechanisms, including antioxidant activity, enzyme inhibition, and insulin-like actions, supporting its potential as a natural therapeutic agent in diabetes management (Maldini et al., 2014).

Figure 3. Pharmacological activities of *Moringa oleifera*

8. Toxicology of *Moringa Oleifera*

Human studies conducted to date have not reported any significant adverse effects. In addition, various preparations of the plant have been widely used worldwide as both food and traditional medicine without documented side effects. Adedapo et al. (2009) reported that oral administration of an aqueous leaf extract to rats at doses ranging from 400 to 2000 mg/kg body weight did not cause mortality; however, a dose-dependent reduction in body weight was observed over a three-week period. Similarly, Awodele et al. (2012) found that an aqueous extract of *M. oleifera* leaves produced no mortality in albino Wistar mice even at high oral doses up to 6400 mg/kg. Nevertheless, administration of higher doses was associated with signs of mild toxicity, including dullness and reduced locomotor activity (Awodele et al., 2012).

9. Uses Of *Moringa oleifera*

Some general uses of *Moringa oleifera* are given below

9.1. Role of *Moringa oleifera* in food industry

Moringa oleifera has numerous industrial and food-related applications due to its rich nutritional and bioactive composition. The seed powder is widely used as a natural

coagulant in water purification, where it helps remove suspended particles and impurities from turbid water. The seed oil is utilized in the production of cosmetics, including soaps and perfumes, and is also explored as a potential source for biodiesel production. In agriculture, *Moringa* extracts containing zeatin are used to promote plant growth and enhance crop yield. In the food industry, *Moringa oleifera* is incorporated into various food and feed products because of its high protein and carbohydrate content. For instance, in Mexico, *Moringa* has been used as a partial replacement for fishmeal in tilapia feed to improve nutritional value while reducing feeding costs. These diverse applications demonstrate the economic and nutritional significance of *Moringa* in food and industrial sectors (Milla et al., 2021).

9.2. Non-Medicinal and Environmental Uses of *Moringa oleifera*

9.2.1. Poultry and Animal Health

M. oleifera is widely utilized in poultry farming for improving animal health and controlling viral, bacterial, and parasitic infections, including Newcastle disease virus. Its use has been associated with reduced mortality and improved livestock productivity (Maldini et al., 2014).

9.2.2. Plant Growth Promotion and Biopesticide Activity

The plant serves as an economical and eco-friendly growth promoter for several crops such as tomatoes, peanuts, maize, and wheat. Studies reported that the use of Moringa leaf extract increased crop yield by approximately 20–35%. Due to the presence of natural growth promoters such as indole acetic acid, gibberellins, cytokinins, and zeatin, Moringa extracts can function as natural alternatives to synthetic fertilizers and pesticides. Methanolic extracts rich in potassium, calcium, carotenoids, phenolic compounds, and zeatin have been shown to improve pod formation, seed production, plant height, and branching in oilseed rape plants. Zeatin, a naturally occurring cytokinin, also contributes to enhanced drought tolerance and growth performance under water-stress conditions.

9.2.3. Water Purification and Environmental Applications

M. oleifera seeds are traditionally used in water treatment due to their coagulating and antimicrobial properties. Studies demonstrated that treatment of river water with Moringa seeds significantly reduced turbidity, hardness, coloration, and microbial contamination, including *Escherichia coli*. Reports also suggest that the plant may serve as a natural alternative to chemical coagulants such as alum for water purification (Maldini et al., 2014).

9.2.4. Plant Disease Management

M. oleifera has shown potential as a natural biopesticide against several plant pathogens. Soil application of Moringa leaves has been reported to suppress *Pythium debaryanum*, the causative organism of damping-off disease in plants (Milla et al., 2021).

9.2.5. Traditional and Spiritual Uses

Different parts of the Moringa plant, including leaves, roots, flowers, fruits, and seeds, have traditionally been used for spiritual and psychological healing practices in various culture (Pareek et al., 2023).

10. Phytopharmaceutical Formulations

Plant-derived extracts have gained considerable attention in pharmaceutical research for the development of therapeutic formulations. The formulation process mainly focuses on achieving product stability and improving patient acceptability and compliance. Extracts of *Moringa oleifera* are considered relatively safe when used within therapeutically recommended doses, which enhances their potential for pharmaceutical applications. Owing to its diverse pharmacological properties and favorable safety profile, *M. oleifera* has been extensively explored for the preparation of different phytopharmaceutical formulations. Various formulation strategies developed using *M. oleifera* have been reported and are summarized below (Stohs and Hartman, 2015).

Plant Part Used	Nature of Extract	Formulation	Method of Preparation and Polymers/Excipients Used	Application	Inference
	The polyherbal formulation exhibited significant anti-ulcer activity.				
	Methanolic extract showed greater anti-inflammatory activity than the aqueous extract. The water-miscible ointment base also demonstrated effective drug diffusion.				
	The micro-dispersion formulation showed enhanced permeation compared to pure oil, with Tween 80 improving permeation efficiency.				
	The lozenge formulation provided convenient administration and improved patient compliance.				

Figure 4. Formulation strategies using *M.oleifera*

11. Future Perspectives

Future research on *Moringa oleifera* should focus on the isolation, characterization, and standardization of its bioactive compounds to better understand their molecular mechanisms and therapeutic potential. Although numerous experimental studies have reported promising pharmacological activities, further large-scale clinical trials are required to establish the efficacy, safety, dosage optimization, and long-term effects of *Moringa*-based formulations in humans. Advanced studies involving nanotechnology, drug delivery systems, and pharmaceutical formulation development may enhance the bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness of *Moringa* phytoconstituents. In addition, more research is needed to evaluate possible herb–drug interactions, toxicity profiles, and quality control parameters for commercial products. The utilization of *Moringa oleifera* in functional foods, nutraceuticals, herbal medicines, cosmetics, and sustainable agricultural practices also offers significant industrial and economic opportunities. With continued scientific exploration and proper standardization, *Moringa oleifera* has the potential to become an

important natural source for future therapeutic and healthcare applications (Milla et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Moringa oleifera is an exceptionally important medicinal plant with remarkable nutritional, pharmacological, and therapeutic potential. The plant contains a wide variety of essential nutrients and bioactive phytochemicals that contribute to its extensive medicinal applications. Different parts of the plant, including leaves, seeds, roots, flowers, bark, and pods, have demonstrated significant biological activities such as antioxidant, anticancer, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and cardioprotective effects. These pharmacological properties are mainly associated with the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, vitamins, and essential minerals. In addition to its medicinal value, *Moringa oleifera* also possesses considerable nutritional and industrial importance, including applications in food supplementation, water purification, cosmetics, and biofuel production. The growing scientific evidence supporting its safety and therapeutic efficacy has increased global interest in its use

as a natural therapeutic agent. Overall, *Moringa oleifera* represents a promising multifunctional plant that may contribute significantly to disease prevention, nutritional improvement, and the development of novel pharmaceutical.

References

- A.HAMID, M. H., MD YUSOFF, M. H., ROSAZLINA, R. & SHAFIE, M. H. 2025. A review on *Moringa oleifera* polysaccharides: Extraction, purification, structure-activity, bioactivities and application. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 323, 147089.
- ABD RANI, N. Z., HUSAIN, K. & KUMOLOSASI, E. 2018. *Moringa* Genus: A Review of Phytochemistry and Pharmacology. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, Volume 9 - 2018.
- ASHRAF, Q., AQIB, A. I., MAJEED, H., HAQ, S. U., NISAR, M. F., USMAN, M., MUNEEER, A., BATOOL, S. & ATAYA, F. S. 2024. Effective synergism of *Moringa oleifera* with antibiotics, body growth, and decoction replacement. *South African Journal of Botany*, 175, 628-636.
- AWODELE, O., OREAGBA, I. A., ODOMA, S., TEIXEIRA DA SILVA, J. A. & OSUNKALU, V. O. 2012. Toxicological evaluation of the aqueous leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. (Moringaceae). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 139, 330-336.
- BHADRESHA, K., THAKORE, V., BRAHMBHATT, J., UPADHYAY, V., JAIN, N. & RAWAL, R. 2022. Anticancer effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaves extract against lung cancer cell line via induction of apoptosis. *Advances in Cancer Biology - Metastasis*, 6, 100072.
- CAMILLERI, E. & BLUNDELL, R. 2024. A comprehensive review of the phytochemicals, health benefits, pharmacological safety and medicinal prospects of *Moringa oleifera*. *Heliyon*, 10, e27807.
- CAO, G., SOFIC, E. & PRIOR, R. L. 1997. Antioxidant and Prooxidant Behavior of Flavonoids: Structure-Activity Relationships. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 22, 749-760.
- DAS, B. R., KURUP, P. A. & NARASIMHA RAO, P. L. 1957. Antibiotic principle from *Moringa pterygosperma*. VII. Antibacterial activity and chemical structure of compounds related to pterygospermin. *Indian J Med Res*, 45, 191-6.
- EILERT, U., WOLTERS, B. & NAHRSTEDT, A. 1981. The antibiotic principle of seeds of *Moringa oleifera* and *Moringa stenopetala*. *Planta Med*, 42, 55-61.
- GÖNENÇ, A., HACIŞEVKİ, A., TAVIL, Y., ÇENGEL, A. & TORUN, M. 2013. Oxidative stress in patients with essential hypertension: A comparison of dippers and non-dippers. *European Journal of Internal Medicine*, 24, 139-144.
- GOPALAKRISHNAN, L., DORIYA, K. & KUMAR, D. S. 2016. *Moringa oleifera*: A review on nutritive importance and its medicinal application. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, 5, 49-56.
- GUEVARA, A. P., VARGAS, C., SAKURAI, H., FUJIWARA, Y., HASHIMOTO, K., MAOKA, T., KOZUKA, M., ITO, Y., TOKUDA, H. & NISHINO, H. 1999. An antitumor promoter from *Moringa oleifera* Lam. *Mutat Res*, 440, 181-8.
- ISLAM, Z., ISLAM, S. M. R., HOSSEN, F., MAHTAB-UL-ISLAM, K., HASAN, M. R. & KARIM, R. 2021. *Moringa oleifera* is a Prominent Source of Nutrients with Potential Health Benefits. *Int J Food Sci*, 2021, 6627265.
- JAISWAL, D., RAI, P. K., MEHTA, S., CHATTERJI, S., SHUKLA, S., RAI, D. K., SHARMA, G., SHARMA, B., KHAIR, S. & WATAL, G. 2013. Role of *Moringa oleifera* in regulation of diabetes-induced oxidative stress. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 6, 426-432.

- KHALID, S., ARSHAD, M., MAHMOOD, S., AHMED, W., SIDDIQUE, F., KHALID, W., ZARLASHT, M., ASAR, T. O. & HASSAN, F. A. 2023. Nutritional and phytochemical screening of Moringa oleifera leaf powder in aqueous and ethanol extract. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 26, 2338-2348.
- KOU, X., LI, B., OLAYANJU, J. B., DRAKE, J. M. & CHEN, N. 2018. Nutraceutical or Pharmacological Potential of Moringa oleifera Lam. *Nutrients*, 10, 343.
- LOPEZ-RODRIGUEZ, N. A., GAYTÁN-MARTÍNEZ, M., DE LA LUZ REYES-VEGA, M. & LOARCA-PIÑA, G. 2020. Glucosinolates and Isothiocyanates from Moringa oleifera: Chemical and Biological Approaches. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr*, 75, 447-457.
- MALDINI, M., MAKSOUD, S. A., NATELLA, F., MONTORO, P., PETRETTO, G. L., FODDAI, M., DE NICOLA, G. R., CHESSA, M. & PINTORE, G. 2014. 'Moringa oleifera: study of phenolics and glucosinolates by mass spectrometry'. *J Mass Spectrom*, 49, 900-10.
- MILLA, P. G., PEÑALVER, R. & NIETO, G. 2021. Health Benefits of Uses and Applications of Moringa oleifera in Bakery Products. *Plants*, 10, 318.
- PAIKRA, B. K., DHONGADE, H. K. J. & GIDWANI, B. 2017. Phytochemistry and Pharmacology of Moringa oleifera Lam. *J Pharmacopuncture*, 20, 194-200.
- PAREEK, A., PANT, M., GUPTA, M. M., KASHANIA, P., RATAN, Y., JAIN, V., PAREEK, A. & CHUTURGOON, A. A. 2023. Moringa oleifera: An Updated Comprehensive Review of Its Pharmacological Activities, Ethnomedicinal, Phytopharmaceutical Formulation, Clinical, Phytochemical, and Toxicological Aspects. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24, 2098.
- SASHIDHARA, K. V., ROSAIAH, J. N., TYAGI, E., SHUKLA, R., RAGHUBIR, R. & RAJENDRAN, S. M. 2009. Rare dipeptide and urea derivatives from roots of Moringa oleifera as potential anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive agents. *Eur J Med Chem*, 44, 432-6.
- SINGH, A. K., RANA, H. K., TSHABALALA, T., KUMAR, R., GUPTA, A., NDHLALA, A. R. & PANDEY, A. K. 2020. Phytochemical, nutraceutical and pharmacological attributes of a functional crop Moringa oleifera Lam: An overview. *South African Journal of Botany*, 129, 209-220.
- SRIVASTAVA, G. & GANJEWALA, D. 2024. An update on the emerging neuroprotective potential of Moringa oleifera and its prospects in complimentary neurotherapy. *Phytomedicine Plus*, 4, 100532.
- STOHS, S. J. & HARTMAN, M. J. 2015. Review of the Safety and Efficacy of Moringa oleifera. *Phytotherapy Research*, 29, 796-804.
- SULTANA, S. 2020. Nutritional and functional properties of Moringa oleifera. *Metabol Open*, 8, 100061.

